

Integrating rotating packed bed (RPB) reactors for efficient CO₂ capture, utilization, and mineralization in industrial clusters

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ABSTRACT

The systematic design of carbon capture, utilization and sequestration (CCUS) systems is important for industrial clusters as the different emitters exhibit variability in terms of emissions intensity and composition. Whereas typically such challenges are addressed by considering heterogeneous technological options both within and between the tiers of the CCUS supply chains, rotating packed beds (RPB) represent an emerging technology that may offer a uniform technological solution across CCUS applications in industrial clusters. RPB are gaining increased attention in solvent-based CO₂ capture as they enable significant reduction of equipment size and overall infrastructure footprint compared to conventional packed bed columns for the same capture efficiency.¹ Additionally, RPB can be used for the production of minerals through carbonation of inorganic oxides with tailored product quality specifications depending on their intended use. For example, RPB have been proposed for the carbonation of calcium-rich industrial slags and wastewater streams, highlighting their potential in utilizing alkaline waste for sustainable CO₂ capture and storage in solid form.² RPB also enable the production of high-value products such as nanosized precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC), hydromagnesite and others, with applications in various industries, such as cement, paper, pharmaceuticals, and nano-composite materials, to name but a few. Their use to this end has significant advantages compared to conventional stirred tank reactors that require chemical additives to achieve the desired nanoparticle structure, exhibit relatively low CO₂ conversion efficiency, and demand extended processing time.³ Industrial clusters that may avail the raw material (e.g., as product or by-product) needed for such products are excellent candidates for the development of RPB-based CCUS infrastructures. The majority of CCUS technologies need to be designed with fixed capacities for the nominal operating settings of the emissions composition and intensity of the cluster stakeholders. RPB unit operations offer significant flexibility as their spinning intensity may be tailored to efficiently address the flue gas variability or product quality specifications, whereas RPB modules can be easily deployed to meet capacity requirements. Existing publications on the design of CCUS networks have not considered the use of RPB in the above context.

This work presents for the first time a framework for the design of an optimal CO₂ capture, utilization, mineralization, and sequestration network within industrial clusters, by incorporating RPB reactors. The framework includes amine-based, post-combustion CO₂ capture as the first route and slurry-based CO₂ mineralization as the second route of flue gas processing options. In the first route, the captured CO₂ may be used as raw material for the production of PCC nanoparticles, it may be used for CO₂ transportation via a low-pressure pipeline grid for subsequent utilization, or it may include compression and pumping, transportation via a high-pressure pipeline grid prior to injection and sequestration. The second route includes minerals transportation via truck and underground burial. The framework is presented as a superstructure-based optimization problem where the constraints primarily represent material and energy balances across individual processes boundaries and network nodes. The objective function minimizes the total annual cost of the whole network, while simultaneously identifying the optimal pathways linking different processes and nodes. The framework is tested in a case study that involves 5 industrial emitters from different industrial sectors, 3 sequestration sites, and one mineral deposit site. Initial results indicate a minimum of 5 % reduction in cost per ton of captured CO₂ for the entire network, compared to a configuration with packed bed reactors for CO₂ capture. This framework serves as a systematic tool guiding the next steps in the widespread deployment of CCUS networks, as it provides a systematic approach to identify the most suitable technological pathways and enhance economic and operational efficiency.

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